

Unaccusatives in Slovenian Impersonals

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Background. Reflexive impersonal constructions in Slovenian show a rather peculiar morphosyntactic restriction on unaccusative verbs, which, while being ungrammatical in their perfective forms (1a), appear to be admissible if used imperfectively (1b).

- (1) a. *Včeraj se je v tej bolnici umrlo.
yesterday REFL is in this hospital died.PFV.N
Intended: “People died in this hospital.”
- b. Včasih se je umiralo od kuge.
once REFL is died.IPFV.N from plague
“People once died from the plague.”

What is important to note is that such impersonals contain a null argument NP (for evidence, see Fehrmann et al. 2010; Rivero and Milojević Sheppard 2003; Szucsich 2008) which interpretatively corresponds to the event undergoer of unaccusatives or the initiator of transitives/unergatives. One popular way (adopted by, e.g., Lavine 2017; Ruda 2014) to account for the contrast in (1) is to assume that there is an aspectual restriction on the felicity of the null NP. Borer (2005) and van Hout (2004) formalise this restriction by positing that the extended VPs of perfectives contain an aspectual phrase with a telicity feature that needs to be matched by a counterpart on the internal argument. However, impersonal NPs are structurally deficient (e.g., they also lack φ -features, Ackema and Neeleman 2018; Fenger 2018; Legate et al. 2020; Rivero and Milojević Sheppard 2003), and do not contain such a matching telicity feature; consequently, impersonals can only host imperfective unaccusatives, in whose case the structurally deficient internal argument does not undergo telicity checking with the aspectual head.

New data. I present new data on the distribution of unaccusatives in Slovenian impersonals that calls into question the aspectual account. The data have been obtained from a corpus investigation into the *metaFida 1.0* corpus (Erjavec 2023), which is a large 6-billion-token meta corpus that unites most existing Slovenian corpora. The corpus investigation, which has checked the occurrence of 51 perfective Slovenian unaccusative verbs (e.g., *umreti* “die”, *prispeti* “arrive”, *izkrvaveti* “bleed out”, *pasti* “fall”) identified by Ilc and Marvin (2016) as well as their imperfective counterparts, unveils two patterns of usage. First, while the majority of the 51 perfective unaccusatives are indeed unattested in the corpus data, 4 appear rather regularly in impersonal constructions – i.e., *prispeti* “arrive”, *priteči* “arrive running”, *preživeti* “survive”, and *pristati* “land”. See, for instance, the corpus example in (2), which contains the perfective unaccusative *prispeti* “arrive” in the first clause.

- (2) Ko se je prispelo do gradbišča, so že čakali delavci.
when REFL is arrived.PFV.N to construction-site AUX.3PL already waited workers.NOM
“When people arrived at the construction site, workers from Dars were already waiting.”

Second, all attested imperfective unaccusatives consistently denote generic or habitually recurring events (either in the present or past domain), as in the corpus example in (3).

- (3) Za take lapsuse se je včasih gorelo
for these mistakes REFL is once burnt.IPFV.N
“People used to burn for such mistakes.”

What is unattested in the corpus data, however, is the non-generic/non-habitual use of imperfective unaccusatives. This empirical gap implies that with a non-iterative progressive interpretation, imperfective unaccusatives should be ungrammatical (Lavine 2005): this indeed seems to

be the case, as shown by the constructed example in (4), where the generic/habitual reading is contextually unavailable.

- (4) * Vstopili smo v bolniško sobo, v kateri se je v tistem trenutku umiralo.
entered.PL AUX.IPL in hospital room in which REFL is in that moment died.IPFV.N
 Intended: “We entered a hospital room in which some people were dying.”

The admissibility of perfective unaccusatives (2), which denote telic eventualities, is surprising on an account where perfectives are ruled out due to the null impersonal NP’s inability to undergo telicity checking. Likewise, the aspectual account predicts that all imperfective unaccusatives should be grammatical in the impersonal construction, which leaves the ungrammaticality of (4) a mystery.

Analysis. I propose that the unaccusative data can be explained if the impersonal construction is analysed as one that necessarily projects the external argument (see also Lavine 2017 for an informal proposal along these lines for the Polish passively marked impersonal construction). Concretely, I claim that the reflexive clitic should be analysed as an active Voice head, which means that it has a c-selectional requirement (in the sense of Bruening 2013, 2021) to merge with both a VP and an NP (i.e., the external argument). The Slovenian reflexive impersonal construction thus has the syntactic skeleton in (5a) at the VoiceP level, where pro_{IMP} corresponds to the null argument. Semantically, the impersonal variant of the reflexive – i.e., se_{IMP} – introduces the Initiator relation (5b) whose individual-type variable x is then quantified over by pro_{IMP} , which is an existential quantifier over humans (Rivero and Milojević Sheppard 2003).

- (5) a. $[_{VoiceP} pro_{IMP} [_{Voice'} se_{IMP} [_{VP} V (NP_{ACC})]]]$
 b. $[[se_{IMP}]^g = \lambda f_{\langle s,t \rangle} \lambda x \lambda e [f(e) \wedge Initiator(e, x)]$

There is independent evidence for positing the reflexive as the exponent of a Voice head, such as the fact that Slovenian reflexive impersonals cannot undergo passivisation, the idea being that the impersonal Voice head (i.e., se_{IMP}) and a passive Voice head are in complementary distribution (Ruda 2014). But what the analysis in (5) also straightforwardly predicts is the ungrammaticality of unaccusatives like *umreti* “die” in (1a). Namely, with unaccusatives, pro_{IMP} is merged inside VP as the internal argument, but the additional merger of se_{IMP} with VP expands the denotation of VP with the Initiator(e, y) relation (6). This incurs a thematic role violation, since *umreti*, being lexically intransitive, has been forced to enter a transitive syntactic frame.

- (6) * $[[Voice']^g \text{ in (1a)} = \lambda y \lambda e \exists x [Undergoer(e, x) \wedge Human(x) \wedge Die(e) \wedge Initiator(e, y)]$

However, the unaccusatives that have been attested in the corpus data – like *prispeti* in (2) – are just those that correspond to complex predications in which the event undergoer is also interpreted as the event initiator (Ramchand 2008b). (Intuitively, one normally has control over an arriving eventuality but not over a dying one.) For such cases, I propose that pro_{IMP} saves the derivation by moving from its internal argument position to Spec, VoiceP. Example (2) thus shows the syntactic derivation in (7a) and the semantic composition in (7b); since the external argument position ends up being filled by pro_{IMP} , the construction is grammatical.

- (7) a. $[_{VoiceP} pro_{IMP} [_{Voice'} se_{IMP} [_{VP} prispeto pro_{IMP}]]]$
 b. $[[VoiceP]^g = \lambda e \exists x [Human(x) \wedge Initiator(e, x) \wedge Arrive(e) \wedge Undergoer(e, x)]$

For the generic examples like (1b) and (3), I propose that their grammaticality is the result of the so-called “generic repair” mechanism (Härtl 2012) also observable in English middles, where sentences that are otherwise ungrammatical under the existential interpretation become licit under a generic (or more broadly, iterative) event reading. Following Schäfer (2007, 2008), I propose that what happens here is that *se* gets reinterpreted (in the sense of contextual allophony, Marantz 2013) into an identity function, but such a reinterpretation can only happen under an iterative operator (8), which corresponds to the head of an aspectual phrase that takes VoiceP as its syntactic complement (Ramchand 2008a).

(8) Under iterative event operators: $\llbracket se_{\text{IMP}} \rrbracket^g = \lambda f_{(s,t)} \lambda e [f(e)]$

Thus, in the case of generic unaccusative impersonals, se_{IMP} no longer turns the denotation of VP into a two-place relation, so no thematic violation arises, and pro_{IMP} moves to Spec, VoiceP just for c-selectional reasons (Schäfer 2007).

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